

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11106453>

CULTURAL FEATURES OF ENGLISH HUMOR

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Annotation. *This work is devoted to the linguistic and cultural characteristics of English humor. The relevance of the work is due to the cultural exchange of English and Uzbek humor. It is important to take into account the fact that English humor is considered difficult to translate and it should be considered by linguistic and cultural features. The purpose of this article is to study the role of linguistic and cultural features of humor in translation from English into Uzbek*

Key words: *English humor, comic effect, culture, laughter, language.*

КУЛЬТУРНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЮМОРА

Аннотация. *Данная работа посвящена лингвокультурным характеристикам английского юмора. Актуальность работы обусловлена культурным обменом английского и узбекского юмора. Нужно учитывать тот факт, что английский юмор считается не простым при переводе и рассматривать нужно с учетом языковых и культурных свойств. Цель настоящей статьи состоит в изучении роли лингвокультурологических особенностей юмора при переводе с английского языка на узбекский язык.*

Ключевые слова: *английский юмор, комический эффект, культура, смех, язык.*

INGLIZ HAJVIYASINING MADANIY XUSUSIYATLARI

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu ilmiy maqola ingliz hajviyasining lingvisvomadaniy xususiyatlariga bog'ishlangan. Ishning dolzarbligi - ingliz va o'zbek hazilining madaniy almashinuvi bilan bog'liq. Shuni inobatga olish kerakki, ingliz hajviyasini tarjima qilishda inglizlarni lingvomadaniy xususiyatlarini inobatga olgan holda tarjima qilish kerak. Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi ingliz tilidan o'zbek tiliga tarjima qilishda hazilning lingvovomadaniy xususiyatlarining rolini o'rganishdir.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ingliz yumor, komik effekt, madaniyat, kulgi, til.*

Language as a cultural phenomenon is studied by linguoculturology, because language is the basis and product of culture. It is in the literary text that fragments of reality are presented. Through the text we can see the spiritual culture of a person and his era. Each text has a specific cultural background that lies behind the words. Civilization, culture, social status - all this leaves its mark on the text. And humor, of course, does not raise doubts about its inclusion in the context of any culture. Humor correlates with one of the most complex categories of aesthetics - the category of the comic, which covers a large group of heterogeneous phenomena, varied in form and content. Humor is often found in literature, theater, cinema and advertising, where the main goal is to make the audience happy. The pleasure of humor, which in naive usage refers to the attitude towards something and the depiction of something in a funny, comic form, has a psychological nature and at the same time eludes psychological explanations. Scottish philosopher of the 19th century A. Bain and English sociologist G. Spencer also viewed laughter as release. They substantiated their judgments by describing the biological mechanisms of laughter. Materials and methods of research. Our work is based on the achievements and methodology of a wide range of literary studies of English literature. The materials for our work were the works of English writers of the twentieth century. Results and discussions. From time immemorial, since the time of Chaucer's Canterbury Tales, writers have made us laugh with their humorous works. The word "humor" itself comes from the humoral medicine of the ancient Greeks, who taught that the balance of fluids in the human body (blood, lymph, yellow and black bile), known as humor, controls human health and emotions. Materials and methods of research. Our work is based on the achievements and methodology of a wide range of literary studies of English literature. The materials for our work were the works of English writers of the twentieth century.

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Results and discussions.

From time immemorial, since the time of Chaucer's Canterbury Tales, writers have made us laugh with their humorous works. The word "humor" itself comes from the humoral medicine of the ancient Greeks, who taught that the balance of fluids in the human body (blood, lymph, yellow and black bile), known as humor, controls human health and emotions. People of all ages and cultures respond to humor. Most people are capable of experiencing humor, that is, having fun, laughing, or smiling at something funny, and therefore they are considered to have a sense of humor. The

importance of laughter for literature, art and culture cannot be overestimated. In the early stages of human history, laughter most clearly manifested itself as a mass phenomenon and was an integral part of holiday rituals. Nonverbal forms of communication, such as music or visual arts, can also be humorous. Humor, of course, is present in literature. Sometimes it is the witty banter of the characters, sometimes the characterization itself or ironic, absurd events that add humorous notes to the work. In a literary work, humor serves many functions. It piques readers' interest, maintains their attention, helps them connect with characters, emphasizes and connects ideas, and helps readers visualize a situation. In literature, humor is a tool that makes the audience laugh or causes amusement or laughter. Its goal is to break monotony, boredom and tediousness, and to relax the reader's nerves. With the help of this tool, writers can also improve the quality of their writing while delighting the audience. Moreover, the most dominant function of humor is to create surprise, which not only improves the quality but also enhances the memorable style of a literary work. Humor is essentially the end product, not the medium itself. The writer uses various techniques, tools, words and sentences to bring out new and funny aspects of life. Usually the following main figurative and expressive means that create humor are distinguished: allegory, hyperbole, farce, sarcasm, irony, pun, litotes, antithesis, oxymoron.

However, national humor has certain characteristics. English humor also has its own specific characteristics, which has come to be perceived as a national trait of the English character. The island way of life, the often-bloody history of the island and climatic conditions had a decisive influence on the formation of the mentality of the modern resident of Foggy Albion. The English character embodied the traits of many peoples who, in one way or another, participated in the life of the British for many centuries. The British in general have a special ability to say strange things with the utmost seriousness. This special gift to the nation is evidenced by the works of the classics of English literature: Shakespeare, Byron, Thackeray, Oscar Wilde, Jerome K. Jerome, Aldous Huxley, etc. Masterly command of the English language, the richness and beauty of the language, subtle humor, often turning into sharp satire is distinguished by the works of George Bernard Shaw. His play "Pygmalion" occupies one of the most prominent places in world drama in terms of originality and artistic grace. The British in general have a special ability to say strange things with the utmost seriousness. This special gift to the nation is evidenced by the works of the classics of English literature: Shakespeare, Byron, Thackeray, Oscar Wilde, Jerome K. Jerome, Aldous Huxley, etc. Masterly command of the English language, the richness and beauty of the language, subtle humor, often turning into sharp satire is distinguished by the works of George Bernard Shaw. His play "Pygmalion" occupies one of the most

prominent places in the world drama in terms of originality and artistic grace. - The rain in Spain stays mainly in the plain. Hurricanes hardly ever happen in Harrow and Hampshire. How kind of you to let me come! – Rain in Spain falls mainly on the plains. Hurricanes almost never occur in Harrow and Hampshire. How kind of you to let me come! But in a fit of enthusiasm for the conversation, she tells the society in detail about her aunt, who was “killed for her straw hat, and who was stolen by someone.” This new style of conversation delights the guests of the salon. Sharp, figurative, original statements of B. Shaw have firmly entered the English language and become aphorisms and proverbs: There are two tragedies in life. One is not to get your heart’s desire. The other is to get it. – There are only two tragedies in life: one is to lose a loved one, the other is to find her. My way of joking is to tell the truth. It is the funniest joke in the world. – My way of joking is to tell the truth.

Oscar Wilde discovered an inexhaustible source of wit in turning ideas inside out:

- "May I ask, Lord Illingworth, do you consider the House of Lords a better institution than the Commons?"

- "Of course, in the House of Lords we never meet public opinion. This is what makes us a cultural institution."

Amazing turnaround phrases from the chapter on the Mad Tea Party:

Then you should say what you mean... I mean what I say. – You should always say what you think - at least I think what I say (translation by N. Demurov) The work of Jerome K. Jerome, the author of the story “Three in a Boat, Not Counting the Dog,” is especially indicative in this sense. Jerome continued the tradition of Dickens, the sphere of his humor is everyday life, the comic adventures of heroes unadapted to practical life, with the world of inanimate things. The story “Three Men in a Boat...” is traditionally considered an example of truly English humor, but such popularity in another language in culture proves that “English humor” is quite successfully transferred to foreign language soil, and, therefore, is based on certain deep foundations. Now, returning to the prospectus on pills, I certainly had all the symptoms of liver disease, the main one being "a general dislike for any kind of work. – Now, returning to the prospectus on pills, I undoubtedly have, there were all the symptoms of liver disease, the main one of which was “a general dislike for all kinds of work.” - But everything has its dark side, as the man whose mother-in-law died when they demanded money for the funeral said. – But everything has its shadow sides, as the man whose mother-in-law died said when they demanded money from him for the funeral. Conclusions. Thus, from the above analysis we can conclude that English literature has deep and long traditions of humor. She is, one might say, full of humor. Almost all major English writers and poets, one way or another, dealt with humor. The

peculiarity of English humorous literature is that it is based on the traditions of folk laughter and is enriched by them. Irony and mockery, gentle humor and the comicality of everyday situations - all this is closely intertwined in works of English literature, reflecting the special flavor of English linguistic culture and the attitude of the British themselves to life.

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